

STUDIES IN ORGANO-ARSENIC COMPOUNDS. PART V. SYNTHESIS OF ARSINDOLE DERIVATIVES.

BY HIRENDRA NATH DAS-GUPTA.

In a previous communication by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 231), the possibility of the synthesis of 1-chloroarsindole from benzene and β -chlorovinylidichloroarsine ($\text{ClCH}=\text{CHAsCl}_2$) has been shown; the intermediate compounds formed from the condensation of the reactants being two mixed arsenicals like β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine (I) and β -chlorovinylidiphenylarsine (II). The present paper is intended to adduce further proof in support of the mechanism of the reaction by the synthesis of the same types of intermediate compounds from a different source. The difference in this case is that one of the reactants already contains arsenic in the nucleus and that the unsaturated grouping has been introduced subsequently. When dry acetylene is passed through freshly distilled phenyldichloroarsine in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, secondary and tertiary arsines are formed as usual (*cf.* Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 305; Green and Price, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 448; Mann and Pope, *ibid.*, 1922, **121**, 1754; Lewis and Stiegler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **47**, 2546). In this case, however, the tertiary arsine was found to be of two different types, *viz.*, a) $\beta\beta'$ -dichlorodivinylphenylarsine (II) and (b) β -chlorovinylidiphenylarsine (III). Avoiding the consideration of the intermediate unstable compound of the arsine with aluminium chloride the reaction probably takes place as follows :

The following scheme shows how the identities of the different compounds have been proved.

(100 g.). The mixture was stirred for 7 hours more, decomposed by 20% cold hydrochloric acid and the oil separating was distilled in *vacuo* several times when the following fractions were collected: (1) 120-30°/3mm., identified to be unchanged phenylarsenious chloride. (2) 135-45°/mm. (75 g.), light yellow oil. (3) 150-55°/4mm., only 2 c.c. (4) 170-78°/5mm. (5) 195-98°/5mm. The different fractions were identified as follows: The oil, b. p. 135-45°/4mm. was identified to be β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine as it produced β -chlorovinyl-diphenylarsine. The m. p. and mixed m. p. of the mercuric chloride double salt of the latter and that prepared synthetically were identical. [Found: C, 38.3; H, 2.7; Cl, 28.6; As, 30.2; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 248.1. $C_8H_7Cl_2As$ requires C, 38.5; H, 2.8; Cl, 28.5; As, 30.12 per cent. M. W., 249].

The fraction boiling at 170-78°/5 mm. was identified to be $\beta\beta'$ -dichlorodivinylphenylarsine. [Found: C, 43.4; H, 3.09; Cl, 25.7; As, 27.6; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 276.1, 275.9. $C_{10}H_9Cl_2As$ requires C, 43.6; H, 3.2; Cl, 25.8; As, 27.2 per cent. M. W., 275.]

Its identity was further confirmed by synthesising it from bromobenzene and $\beta\beta'$ -dichlorodivinylchloroarsine as follows: A solution of $\beta\beta'$ -dichlorodivinylchloroarsine (11 g.) in ether was added drop by drop to the Grignard reagent from bromobenzene (7 g.) and magnesium (1.2 g.) in ether (50 c.c.); each drop reacted with slight explosive violence with the formation of a white precipitate, which dissolved on shaking. But the reaction was not so violent towards the end. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 1 hour and then decomposed by cold water; the ethereal layer washed successively with dilute hydrochloric acid, sodium hydroxide solution, water, dried over calcium chloride, and distilled at 165-80°/3mm. [Found: As, 27.1; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 268. $C_{10}H_9Cl_2As$ requires As, 27.2 per cent. M.W., 275].

β -Chlorovinyl-diphenylarsine.--The fraction at 190-95°/5mm. was identified to be the desired compound. It gives a mercuric chloride double salt, the m.p. and mixed m.p. 238°, being identified with that prepared synthetically (*cf.* Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 231) (Found: As, 25.6. $C_{14}H_{12}ClAs$ requires As, 25.8 per cent).

Derivatives of β -Chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine.

β -Chlorovinylphenylarsinic acid was obtained by treating β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine with excess of hydrogen peroxide (3vol.) in glacial acetic acid and after keeping overnight the solution was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and the residual pasty mass was dried on a porous plate and

crystallised from a mixture of acetone and carbon tetrachloride, m.p. 135°. (Found: As, 30.3. $C_8H_9O_2ClAs$ requires As, 30.4 per cent).

β -Chlorovinylphenylarsine ethylether [$PhAs(OEt)CH:CHCl$] was prepared by heating for 20 minutes a freshly prepared alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide (3.5 g.) and a solution of β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine (12 g.) in absolute alcohol (25 c.c.). The precipitate formed was filtered off and the major portion of the solvent removed by evaporation under reduced pressure. The yellow oil obtained by adding water was distilled at 165-70°/3mm. [Found: Cl, 13.2; As, 28.9; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 261.3. $C_{10}H_{12}OClAs$ requires Cl, 13.7; As, 29.01 per cent. M.W., 258.5].

β -Chlorovinylphenylarsenious Cyanide was obtained by heating for 2 hours a mixture of β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine and excess of potassium cyanide in absolute alcohol. The solution on dilution with water gave a yellow liquid. (Found: As, 31.17. C_9H_7NCIAs requires As, 31.3 per cent).

β -Chlorovinylphenylarsenious Sulphide ($ClCH = CHAs-S-AsCH = CHCl$).—A solution of β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine in absolute alcohol was saturated for 5 hours with dry sulphuretted hydrogen and yellow viscous oil separating was washed with alcohol. It was dissolved in acetone and treated with excess of petroleum ether and allowed to stand when needles separated, which were recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 141°. (Found: As, 32.8. $C_{16}H_{14}Cl_2As_2S$ requires As, 32.6 per cent).

β -Chlorovinyl-diphenylarsine (III).—It was obtained by adding ethereal solution of β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine (9.6 g.) to the Grignard reagent from bromobenzene (6 g.) and magnesium (9 g.). The liquid obtained was distilled at 195-98°/4mm. The mercuric chloride double salt melts at 238°. (Found: As, 25.6. $C_{14}H_{12}ClAs$ requires As, 25.8 per cent).

β -Chlorovinylphenylmethylarsine was prepared from β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine and magnesium methyl iodide. It is a light yellow oil of unpleasant odour. (Found: As, 32.4. $C_9H_{10}ClAs$ requires As, 32.8 per cent).

Derivatives of $\beta\beta'$ -Dichlorodivinylphenylarsine.

The mercuric chloride double salt was obtained as a white precipitate by adding $\beta\beta'$ -dichlorodivinylphenylarsine in ether to the molecular proportion of mercuric chloride in the same solvent. The precipitate formed was washed with ether and crystallised as needles from hot alcohol, m.p. 157-58°. (Found: Hg, 36.5. $C_{10}H_8Cl_4AsHg$ requires Hg, 36.8 per cent).

The silver nitrate double salt was obtained by heating alcoholic solution

of $\beta\beta'$ -dichlorodivinylphenylarsine and silver nitrate for 2 hours on a water-bath. The solution was poured into ether and filtered from the precipitated mass, which melts indefinitely at $205-12^\circ$. The mother liquor on further dilution with ether gave a pasty white precipitate, which was dried on a porous plate and crystallised from alcohol as clustered needles, m.p. 170° . (Found: Ag, 23.9. $C_{10}H_9O_3NCl_2AgAs$ requires Ag, 24.2 per cent).

$\beta\beta'$ -Dichlorodivinylphenylmethylarsonium Iodide (IV).— $\beta\beta'$ -Dichlorodivinylphenylarsine was heated in a sealed tube on the water-bath with excess of methyl iodide for 2 hours. The crystals separating were collected and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 232° . (Found: As, 17.28. $C_{11}H_{12}Cl_2AsI$ requires As, 17.9 per cent).

Arsindole Derivatives.

1-Chloroarsindole.—(a) It was prepared (cf. part IV) from β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in dry carbon disulphide. The fraction boiling at $135^\circ-40/5$ mm. was collected.

(b) β -Chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine (10 c. c.) was heated under reflux for 4 hours at $230^\circ-40^\circ$ when hydrogen chloride was evolved. The black mass was extracted several times with ether, the solvent evaporated off and the oil distilled at $132^\circ-140/5$ mm. [Found: As, 35.1; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 217.4. C_8H_6ClAs requires As, 35.2 per cent. M.W., 212.5].

1-Methylarsindole was prepared in accordance with the method given in Part IV. The mercuric chloride double compound melts at $150-51^\circ$, identical with that from other source. (Found: As, 39.1. C_9H_9As requires As, 39.06 per cent). Picrate, m.p. and mixed m.p. $106-7^\circ$.

1-Ethylarsindole.—It was prepared from 1-chloroarsindole and ethyl magnesium iodide in a manner similar to that for 1-methylarsindole. The compound was extracted with ether, the solvent removed and the oil distilled at $138-45^\circ/6$ mm. Like the methyl derivative it also possesses a very strong offensive smell and produces blister on the skin which is very difficult to heal. [Found: As, 36.3; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 210. $C_{10}H_{11}As$ requires As, 36.4 per cent. M.W., 206]. It readily gives a picrate, m.p. $100-2^\circ$.

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